

4Q299 frag. 3a ii lines 3-4 + PAM 43.672 frag. 67 (join)

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small section from 4Q299 frag. 3a ii lines 3-4 (IAA Plate 605, frag. 3)
and PAM 43.672 frag. 67 (IAA Plate 83, frag. 76)

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-482758>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-493499>

4Q299	<i>Qumran Cave 4, XV: Sapiential Texts, Part 1</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 20 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1997), 29-97
PAM 43.672	Dana Pike and Andrew Skinner, <i>Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2001), 55-60.
IAA	Israel Antiquities Authority (used for reference to Plate numbers with scrolls fragments). IAA images in The Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, deadseascrolls.org.il
PAM	Palestine Archaeological Museum (used for references to PAM photographs).